

FOREST4EU partner: Cesefer

OG: SUBER

OG's country: Spain

Type of Innovation: Product

Quality cork guide

Introduction

Gosuber project, developed from 2018 to 2020, has been oriented to improve cork harvesting efficiency. Furthermore, at GOSUBER other uses of cork have been studied, apart from wine corking, the aeronautical industry, construction, and other minor uses, to improve the marketing and valuation of cork.

Currently, much of the economic value of cork lies in its capacity to manufacture wine stoppers but, given its exceptional physical-chemical properties, there are multiple possibilities for use in areas as diverse as the aeronautical industry or cosmetics. ; The resulting products provide a very high added value compared to traditional uses and represent a very significant economic potential for rural areas (creation of qualified work, stopping rural depopulation, industrialization of the economy, etc.) as well as the maintenance of the ecosystems of the cork oak forests. Main results have been materialized in a guide to new uses of cork with the studies carried out and their applications.

Lessons learned

The valorization of cork, on the rise due to the general decline of cork oak forests and the advance in the technology of manufacturing technological wine stoppers (where almost all cork quality classifications are valid), complicates its use for applications outside of the wine market

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://gosuber.es/>

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